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Additional Information

Modeling the effect of glucagon on endogenous glucose production in type 1 diabetes: on the role of glucagon receptor dynamics

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ABSTRACT

This paper validates a glucoregulatory model including glucagon receptors dynamics in the description of endogenous glucose production (EGP). A set of models from literature are selected for a head-to-head comparison in order to evaluate the role of glucagon receptors. Each EGP model is incorporated into an existing glucoregulatory model and validated using a set of clinical data, where both insulin and glucagon are administered. The parameters of each EGP model are identified in the same optimization problem, minimizing the root mean square error (RMSE) between the simulation and the clinical data. The results show that the RMSE for the proposed receptors-based EGP model was lower when compared to each of the considered models (Receptors approach: 7.13 ± 1.71 mg/dl vs. 7.76 ± 1.45 mg/dl ($p = 0.066$), 8.45 ± 1.38 mg/dl ($p = 0.011$) and 8.99 ± 1.62 mg/dl ($p = 0.007$)). This raises the possibility of considering glucagon receptors dynamics in type 1 diabetes simulators.

1. Introduction

People with type 1 diabetes (T1D) suffer from an impairment in their blood glucose (BG) regulation. Due to the auto-immune destruction of the β cells in the pancreas, insulin is not produced, which is the hormone responsible of promoting glucose uptake by the cells. As a result, the body is unable to restore glucose concentration to normal values. People with T1D rely on external insulin administration with insulin pens or infusion pumps in order to regulate their BG levels. However, high doses of insulin could lead to low BG concentration if overdosed. Both a maintained high BG concentration (hyperglycaemia), and a low BG concentration (hypoglycaemia) are undesirable situations. The former, because it can cause several long-term vascular complications, such as retinopathy, foot amputations, heart attack and strokes, nephropathy, neuropathy, among others. Meanwhile, hypoglycaemia could induce dizziness, nausea, coma or even death in the most severe cases (Cryer et al., 2003). This means people with T1D live with the colossal task of self-managing their diabetes on a daily basis.

In order to ease this duty, automated insulin delivery systems (also known as artificial pancreases (APs)) have recently appeared on the market. This term refers to the combination of (at least) three different elements: an insulin pump, a continuous glucose monitor (CGM) and a

control algorithm (incorporated in the pump or in an external device such as a smartphone). The algorithm receives the glucose values provided by the CGM and provides an insulin infusion value to the pump every few minutes, according to a given control logic. Despite automation, hypoglycaemia prevention is challenging for single-hormone (insulin-only) systems, especially in situations like exercise or when overdosed. Thus, additional counterregulatory actions are needed, such as, intake of rescue carbohydrates or administration of glucagon.

Glucagon is a hormone produced in the pancreas by the α cells with an antagonist effect to insulin (it increases glucose concentration), promoting endogenous glucose production (EGP). The glucagon secretion is also impaired in people with T1D mainly due to the lack of signaling between β and α cells (Unger and Cherrington, 2012). Glucagon is often used as stand-alone injections to rapidly rise glucose levels in case of severe hypoglycaemia. Soluble formulations of glucagon (Hövelmann et al., 2018) have paved the way to dual-hormone AP systems infusing glucagon through dual-chamber pumps or an additional pump, in order to prevent hypoglycaemia. Dual-hormone APs have proven useful in glucose regulation in contrast to single-hormone APs, especially under exercise (Weisman et al., 2017; Peters and Haidar, 2018). Integrating glucagon in APs allows to regulate glucose as the pancreas would, without needing any patient intervention, as it would be the case with the intake of rescue carbohydrates.

A fundamental step in the development of AP systems is the use of simulation tools to validate the algorithms. Clinical trials are expensive and may entail risks for the patients. Therefore, a lot of effort has been put towards

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developing mathematical models that reproduce physiology as accurately as possible. The use of these simulators allows to test algorithms in a quick and inexpensive way. The most commonly used models in the validation of AP algorithms are Dalla Man's model (Dalla Man et al., 2014) (the UVA/Padova simulator) and Hovorka's model (Wilinska et al., 2010) (the Cambridge simulator and with some variations, OHSU and McGill simulators, for instance).

Whereas pharmacokinetics of insulin and glucagon are described in a similar fashion, other aspects can differ greatly among authors, such as EGP. This quantity is influenced by both insulin and glucagon and represents glucose production as a response to either hypoglycaemia or hyperglycemia. However, contrary to insulin, whose dynamics have been widely studied and there is a consensus in literature about describing its effect (Hovorka et al., 2002; Dalla Man et al., 2014), glucagon effect description is more diverse. Although both insulin and glucagon are involved in EGP, their relationship has been described very differently in literature, and not many clinical trials study the relationship between both hormones. Their influence on EGP has been described as additive (Resalat et al., 2019), multiplicative (Emami et al., 2017), or with a Michaelis-Menten function (Wendt et al., 2017).

El Youssef et al. (2014) reported a loss of glucagon effectiveness for high insulinemia under constant insulin infusion. A vanishing effect of glucagon effectiveness has also been reported. Whereas it has been proved that insulin and glucagon have a collaborative relationship, its physiological extent and mathematical description is still debated. One element that is sometimes overlooked in AP simulators development is glucagon receptors. The work by Masroor et al. (2019) gave some insight into their dynamics.

The purpose of this work is to test an unconventional method for describing glucagon behaviour. A physiology-based structure may prove useful in describing glucose dynamics more accurately. The glucagon receptors-based EGP model is compared to three other EGP models from literature. A set of clinical data is used to fit the models and to identify their parameters. In previous work, the authors carried out the validation of the receptors approach against just one other description of EGP (Furió-Novejarque et al., 2022). This work adds two extra models to the comparison and changes the identification process so that the parameters in the baseline model used are common for all EGP definitions (the previous approach identified the models independently). The process will show how the receptors approach provides a good fit to the data, reducing the average error compared to the other models.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the base model and the different EGP descriptions used for validation. Section 3 presents the identification procedure, divided into the description of the clinical data and the parameter identification method. Section 4 shows the main results and Section 5 discusses the implications of the results. Section 6 summarizes the conclusions.

2. Models

The evaluation of the EGP models was carried out using a baseline model that included descriptions of glucose regulation, insulin pharmacokinetics and glucagon pharmacokinetics. The submodel corresponding to EGP and glucagon effect was instantiated with the different EGP models to be evaluated.

Wendt et al. (2017) presented the model used as reference, which is based on the widely used model by Hovorka et al. (2002). However, the former also incorporates glucagon pharmacokinetics and its effect on glucose. This model also fitted the purpose of the paper since it was identified using the same clinical dataset that is used to validate this work. Experimental data was obtained by Ranjan et al. (2016) and it is described in more detail in Section 3.1.

The other EGP structures selected for comparison were chosen because their underlying structures were also based on Hovorka's model of glucose regulation. A total of four different definitions of EGP and glucagon effect are tested in this work:

1. The definition by Wendt et al. (2017), which accompanies the baseline model. It will be labeled as *DTU* (Technical University of Denmark) which was Wendt's affiliation at the time of publication.
2. The EGP model proposed by Emami et al. (2017). This paper evaluates several definitions of EGP and presents a solution that is the one used in this work. It will be labeled as *McGill*, for McGill University in Montreal.
3. The proposal by Resalat et al. (2019), which was first presented in Jacobs et al. (2015). It will be referred to as *OHSU* model, for the Oregon Health and Science University.
4. EGP based on receptors dynamics, this paper's new proposal, following the work by Masroor et al. (2019). It will be labeled as *Receptors* model.

The next sections will describe the baseline model and each one of the EGP definitions.

2.1. Baseline model

The baseline model can be divided into four different blocks: insulin pharmacokinetics, glucagon pharmacokinetics, EGP, and glucose regulation.

Figure 1 provides an overview of the model compartments and their relationships. The block corresponding to EGP is left empty since its content will depend on the model being evaluated. Next, the equations and states of each subsystem are presented. Also, the model states are described in Table 1 and the parameters and their description can be found in Table 2.

2.1.1. Insulin pharmacokinetics

The insulin pharmacokinetics subsystem (blue block, Figure 1) consists of two compartments ($X_1(t)$ and $X_2(t)$), the input being the insulin infusion ($u_I(t)$), expressed as a deviation with respect to basal insulin infusion, and the

Figure 1: Baseline model overview. Glucose regulation (red box), insulin pharmacokinetics (blue box) and glucagon pharmacokinetics (green box), corresponding to the model definition by Wendt et al. (2017). The EGP definition varies between the four definitions studied in this work (see Sections 2.2 to 2.5).

Table 1
Baseline model states units and description.

Magnitude	Units	Description
$u_I(t)$	U/min	Insulin infusion (as a deviation from basal)
$X_1(t)$	U	Insulin mass due to exogenous dosing in subcutaneous tissue
$X_2(t)$	U	Insulin mass due to exogenous dosing in plasma
$I(t)$	mU/l	Insulin plasma concentration
$u_C(t)$	pg/min	Glucagon infusion (as a deviation from basal)
$Z_1(t)$	pg	Glucagon mass due to exogenous dosing in subcutaneous tissue
$Z_2(t)$	pg	Glucagon mass due to exogenous dosing in plasma
$C(t)$	pg/ml	Glucagon concentration in plasma
$x_1(t)$	mU/l	Effect of insulin on glucose distribution
$x_2(t)$	mU/l	Effect of insulin on glucose disposal
$x_3(t)$	mU/l	Effect of insulin on endogenous glucose production
$EGP(t)$	$\mu\text{mol/kg/min}$	Endogenous glucose production
$Q_1(t)$	$\mu\text{mol/kg}$	Glucose mass in the accessible compartment
$Q_2(t)$	$\mu\text{mol/kg}$	Glucose mass in the non-accessible compartment
$G(t)$	mmol/l	Blood glucose

Table 2
Baseline model parameters units and description.

Parameter	Units	Description
t_{max}	min	Time from dose to maximum plasma concentration
W	kg	Weight
$Cl_{F,I}$	ml/kg/min	Apparent insulin clearance
I_b	mU/l	Basal insulin concentration
k_1, k_2	min^{-1}	Absorption elimination rate constants
$Cl_{F,C}$	ml/kg/min	Apparent glucagon clearance
C_b	pg/ml	Basal glucagon concentration
k_{a1}, k_{a2}, k_{a3}	min^{-1}	Deactivation rate constants
F_{0I}	$\mu\text{mol/kg/min}$	Insulin-independent glucose flux
F_R	$\mu\text{mol/kg/min}$	Renal glucose clearance
S_T	$\text{min}^{-1}/(\text{mU/l})$	Insulin sensitivity to glucose transport
S_D	$\text{min}^{-1}/(\text{mU/l})$	Insulin sensitivity to glucose disposal
k_{12}	min^{-1}	Transfer rate constant from the non-accessible to the accessible compartment
V	ml/kg	Glucose distribution volume

$$\frac{dX_1(t)}{dt} = u_I(t) - \frac{X_1(t)}{t_{max}} \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{dX_2(t)}{dt} = \frac{X_1(t)}{t_{max}} - \frac{X_2(t)}{t_{max}} \quad (1b)$$

$$I(t) = \frac{1}{t_{max}} \frac{X_2(t)}{W \cdot Cl_{F,I}} \cdot 10^6 + I_b \quad (1c)$$

output, plasma insulin concentration ($I(t)$). The factor 10^6 in (1c) acts as unit conversion from U/ml to mU/l (Wendt et al., 2017).

2.1.2. Glucagon pharmacokinetics

The glucagon pharmacokinetics (green block, Figure 1) is also represented as a two-compartment subsystem ($Z_1(t)$ and $Z_2(t)$), analogously to the insulin one, with input the glucagon infusion ($u_C(t)$), expressed as a deviation with respect to basal glucagon infusion (which is expected to be zero), and output plasma glucagon concentration ($C(t)$).

$$\frac{dZ_1(t)}{dt} = u_C(t) - k_1 \cdot Z_1(t) \quad (2a)$$

$$\frac{dZ_2(t)}{dt} = k_1 \cdot Z_1(t) - k_2 \cdot Z_2(t) \quad (2b)$$

$$C(t) = \frac{k_2 \cdot Z_2(t)}{W \cdot Cl_{F,C}} + C_b \quad (2c)$$

2.1.3. Glucose regulation

The glucose regulation subsystem (red block, Figure 1) follows the Hovorka model (Hovorka et al., 2002). It is composed by three states representing the effects of insulin on EGP, glucose transport, and glucose uptake.

$$\frac{dx_1(t)}{dt} = k_{a1} (I(t) - x_1(t)) \quad (3a)$$

$$\frac{dx_2(t)}{dt} = k_{a2} (I(t) - x_2(t)) \quad (3b)$$

$$\frac{dx_3(t)}{dt} = k_{a3} (I(t) - x_3(t)) \quad (3c)$$

Finally, the glucose dynamics for the accessible, $Q_1(t)$, and non-accessible, $Q_2(t)$, compartments, are described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dQ_1(t)}{dt} = & -F_{01}(t) - F_R(t) - S_T \cdot x_1(t) \cdot Q_1(t) \\ & + k_{12} \cdot Q_2(t) + EGP(t) \end{aligned} \quad (3d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dQ_2(t)}{dt} = & S_T \cdot x_1(t) \cdot Q_1(t) \\ & - Q_2(t) (k_{12} + S_D \cdot x_2(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (3e)$$

$$G(t) = \frac{Q_1(t)}{V} \quad (3f)$$

where the definition of $EGP(t)$ will vary depending on the model used. Note that, as compared to Hovorka et al. (2002), equations (3a)-(3c) have unit static gain, being insulin sensitivities (gains) for glucose transport and uptake described by parameters S_T and S_D , respectively, in equations (3d)-(3e). Hepatic insulin sensitivity will be defined by the corresponding model describing $EGP(t)$.

The following sections describe the different EGP models tested in this study. In the presentation of the subsequent models, the notation of parameters and states has been kept as similar as possible to the original respective works for the sake of clarity, as listed in Table 3.

2.2. DTU EGP model

The original Wendt model (Wendt et al., 2017) described EGP as:

$$EGP(t) = G_{gg}(t) + G_{GNG} \quad (4a)$$

Figure 2: DTU EGP model.

where the signal $G_{gg}(t)$ determines the effect of glucagon and insulin on hepatic glucose production. This relationship is given by a Michaelis-Menten expression with maximum rate inhibited by insulin effect ($x_3(t)$) above basal insulin concentration I_b , with hepatic insulin sensitivity S_E :

$$\begin{aligned} G_{gg}(t) = & \frac{1 - S_E \cdot x_3(t)}{1 - S_E \cdot I_b} \cdot \\ & \left((E_{max} - G_{GNG}) \frac{C(t)}{C_{E50} + C(t)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4b)$$

2.3. McGill EGP model

Figure 3: McGill EGP model.

Emami et al. (2017) perform a comparison of 8 different descriptions of $EGP(t)$ and validates them with a set of clinical data. The model concluded as the best description for EGP was defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} EGP(t) = & H((1 - S \cdot x_3(t)) \cdot \\ & H(EGP_G(t) + T \cdot C(t)) + G_{ng} \end{aligned} \quad (5a)$$

where $H(\cdot)$ is the unit step function, included to keep the expression positive. They consider that not only the level of plasma glucagon contributes to hepatic glucose production, but also its rate of change, defining the derivative of $EGP_G(t)$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dEGP_G(t)}{dt} = & -k_{Gd} \cdot EGP_G(t) \\ & - k_{Gd} \cdot T_{Gd} \left(\frac{dC(t)}{dt} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5b)$$

Hepatic insulin sensitivity is given by parameter S . Similarly to Wendt et al. (2017), insulin effect $x_3(t)$ inhibits glucagon effect on EGP as a multiplicative factor.

Figure 4: OHSU EGP model.

2.4. OHSU EGP model

Jacobs et al. (2015) proposed a model based on Hovorka's model (Hovorka et al., 2002), incorporating glucagon dynamics. However, contrary to Wendt et al. (2017), EGP is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} EGP(t) = & EGP_0(1 - S_f \cdot x_3(t) + Y(t) \\ & + k_{g3} \cdot \frac{dY(t)}{dt}) \end{aligned} \quad (6a)$$

where $Y(t)$ represents glucagon effect with dynamics given by:

$$\frac{dY(t)}{dt} = k_c \cdot C(t) - k_d \cdot Y(t) \quad (6b)$$

Note that the parameter S_f was added to the original formulation of the model, in order to match our definition of the unit-gain $x_3(t)$, as compared to Jacobs et al. (2015). Also, units of k_c are different with respect to the original definition, in order to match the units of the plasma glucagon signal.

Remark that, contrary to Wendt et al. (2017) and Emami et al. (2017), insulin and glucagon effects on EGP in this model are considered to be additive, instead of multiplicative. This means that contribution of glucagon to EGP is independent of insulin, and that the balance between glucagon and insulin antagonistic effects will determine EGP.

2.5. Receptors-based EGP model

Figure 5: Receptors EGP model.

More recently, the work from Masroor et al. (2019) proposed a three compartment system to describe glucagon receptors dynamics. Receptors are located on the surface membrane of the liver and they bond to plasma glucagon.

This pairing triggers a chain of protein signaling that results in promoting glycogenolysis and glyconeogenesis (Müller et al., 2017). After this, glucagon-bond receptors dissociate and internalize at different rates, becoming temporarily unavailable in this latter case. The authors represent this process with a three compartment model, one state variable for each state of the receptors: available ($r(t)$), bonded to glucagon/active ($r_c(t)$) and internalized ($r_i(t)$). Assuming that the total number of receptors, although unknown, remains constant, this relationship can be simplified considering the constraint $r_i(t) = 1 - r(t) - r_c(t)$, where the state variables are expressed as relative to the total number of receptors. As a result, a two-compartment model is obtained describing unbound and bonded (active) receptors, which is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dr(t)}{dt} = & -k_{on} \cdot V_h \cdot C(t) \cdot r(t) + k_{off} \cdot r_c(t) \\ & + k_{rec}(1 - r(t) - r_c(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (7a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dr_c(t)}{dt} = & k_{on} \cdot V_h \cdot C(t) \cdot r(t) - k_{off} \cdot r_c(t) \\ & - k_{in} \cdot r_c(t) \end{aligned} \quad (7b)$$

Then, glucagon effect on hepatic glucose production ($F_{hgp}(t)$) is made dependent on active glucagon receptors, as opposed to previous models which consider plasma glucagon concentration. This relation is modeled by means of a Michaelis-Menten relationship, as follows:

$$F_{hgp}(t) = \frac{V_r \cdot r_c(t)}{K_r + r_c(t)} \quad (7c)$$

When incorporating this effect into our model, the EGP expression was complemented by adding an additive effect of insulin on glucose production by the liver, which was not considered in the work by Masroor et al. (2019). With this, the expression of EGP is finally constituted as:

$$EGP(t) = F_{hgp}(t) + EGP_0(1 - S_I \cdot x_3(t)) \quad (7d)$$

where S_I is the hepatic insulin sensitivity.

The original work by Masroor et al. (2019) validated the model with glucagon-challenge test data on eight healthy subjects, and used a minimal glucoregulatory model, based on the Bergman et al. (1981) model. In this work, it is incorporated into a more detailed model and it is validated using data from people with T1D receiving subcutaneous glucagon injection of various doses, better describing the expected use of glucagon, as explained in the next section. This model proposal has already been proven useful in describing glucagon dynamics, as shown in the authors' previous work (Furió-Novejarque et al., 2022).

3. Identification procedure

3.1. Clinical data

The data used for the models evaluation was obtained in a clinical trial performed by Ranjan et al. (2016). The purpose

Figure 6: Protocol in the clinical trial by Ranjan et al. (2016). After admission, patients were administered insulin in order to lower their glycemic values to 70 mg/dl. When glucose reached hypoglycaemia conditions ($t = 0$ min) a glucagon or saline bolus was injected.

of the trial was to test the efficacy of different glucagon doses in recovering from mild hypoglycaemia. Eight subjects with T1D took part in the study, who underwent four different arms in the trial.

The protocol for the study was the following: patients received an insulin bolus to reach mild hypoglycemic conditions (BG concentration lower than 70 mg/dl). At that point they received either saline or a glucagon bolus (100 μ g, 200 μ g or 300 μ g) depending on the trial arm. A summary of the protocol is shown in Figure 6. Plasma glucose, plasma glucagon, plasma insulin, plasma growth hormone, cortisol, free fatty acids, triglycerides, blood pressure, and heart rate were measured throughout the study. In the development of this work, only the information about plasma glucose, glucagon and insulin was used. Also, since the main interest was the modeling of glucagon effect on EGP, only the visits were glucagon was administered (100 μ g, 200 μ g or 300 μ g) have been considered, which will be labeled as visit A, B and C henceforth.

3.2. Parameter identification

The main goal of this work is to test the receptors structure capability of describing observed glucose behavior against other proposals. This required identifying the model-specific parameters for each one of the aforementioned EGP models.

In a previous work, where a preliminary validation of the EGP model based on glucagon receptors was carried out, the identification was performed independently for each of the two models being tested (Furió-Novejarque et al., 2022). However, since there are multiple EGP definitions, but the baseline model is common to all of them, the identification was revised taking into account that:

1. The parameters in the baseline model should be the same for each one of the complete models.
2. Instead of carrying out separate optimizations for each one of the models, the required set of parameters should be found for all of the models in the same optimization problem. This way, the parameters of the base model will be common to all EGP definitions.

3. The aim is to test each model structure, not finding a global model for all the patients. Hence, a different set of parameters will be identified for each patient.

With these premises in mind, the proposed identification method tries to find the best fit to the data for all the models while being equally fair. Note that most of the parameters for the baseline model (Table 2) are taken from Wendt et al. (2017), since they used the same set of clinical data as the present work.

In solving the optimization problem, each model runs three times, one for each visit to the clinic. Then, for each model, an index was calculated as the aggregated sum of the root mean square error (RMSE) per visit:

$$J_m = \sum_{v=1}^3 \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_v} \sum_{i=1}^{n_v} (\hat{y}_{i,P}^v - y_{i,P}^v)^2} \quad (8)$$

where m refers to the models, v refers to the visits, n_v is the number of data points in a specific visit, P refers to the patient, $\hat{y}_{i,P}^v$ is the simulated data point and $y_{i,P}^v$ is the measured data.

The total index to be optimized was the average value of J_m for the four models.

$$J = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \sum_{m=1}^4 J_m \quad (9)$$

Regarding the parameters to be identified, insulin sensitivities (S_T and S_D , (3d)-(3e)) were identified not only per patient but also per visit (i.e., each patient gets a different insulin sensitivity in each visit to the clinic). The reason behind this is that insulin sensitivity can present a wide variability, and change along time for a myriad of reasons (Heinemann, 2002). Along with these parameters, the initial condition for the state $Q_2(t)$ (Q_{2_0}) was also identified for each visit. This allows to have a better fit to the data of each visit especially in the first part of the trial, where only insulin effect is present. In this way, simulated glucose and real glucose will be the closest possible at time $t = 0$ min, since from that point onwards is where our main area of interest will be.

The total vector of parameters can be divided into different sections. The first subset of parameters to identify will contain the constants from the base model.

$$\theta_{1P}^v = \{S_T^v, S_D^v, Q_{2_0}^v\}, \quad v = 1, 2, 3; \quad P = 1, 2, \dots, 8$$

For each of the EGP models, a subset of parameters is selected to be identified. These sets are identified per patient, but they are common across visits (the same EGP model should be able to explain the response of different glucagon doses). First, the subset for the DTU model will be:

$$\theta_{2P} = \{G_{NG}, S_E, E_{max}, C_{E50}\}, \quad P = 1, 2, \dots, 8$$

For the McGill model:

$$\theta_{3P} = \{G_{ng}, S, T, K_{Gd}, T_{Gd}\}, \quad P = 1, 2, \dots, 8$$

For the OHSU model:

$$\theta_{4P} = \{EGP_0, S_f, k_{g3}, k_g, k_c\}, \quad P = 1, 2, \dots, 8$$

And finally the receptors model:

$$\theta_{5P} = \{EGP_0, S_I, k_{on}, K_r, V_r\}, \quad P = 1, 2, \dots, 8$$

The receptors model included many parameters describing rates between the receptors compartments. In the original work by Masroor et al. (2019), some of the parameters were identified whereas others were fixed according to previous works found in literature, based on the modeling of insulin receptors (k_{rec} based on Sedaghat et al. (2002)) or previous studies on glucagon receptors (k_{on} and k_{off} based on Ronald Kahn (1976)). However, it was deemed appropriate to identify the activation rate (k_{on} , (7a)-(7b)) as a way of tailoring the process to each patient. Furthermore, to avoid identifiability issues, the value of k_{in} was fixed to the identified value in Masroor et al. (2019). The components of the Michaelis-Menten expression (K_r and V_r , (7c)), were also included in the identification.

The complete parameter vector to be optimized will include all parameter subsets.

$$\theta_P = \{\theta_{1P}^1, \theta_{1P}^2, \theta_{1P}^3, \theta_{2P}, \theta_{3P}, \theta_{4P}, \theta_{5P}\}$$

This leaves an optimization problem with a total of 28 parameters per patient. The identification was carried out using the `fmincon` function in Matlab R2018b. This function makes use of the interior point algorithm to find the minimum of the specified cost index (9) (Nocedal and Wright, 2006). This algorithm is the default solver in the `fmincon` function, and it is widely used for solving optimization problems. The interior point algorithm tries to iteratively approach the optimal solution from the interior of a feasible set. Since this is a local optimization solver, the optimization was repeated five times with different random starting points within the parameter bounds. These bounds are predefined based on the provided parameter values in each model's original work.

To solve the system of differential equations, Matlab provides the function `ode45`, that makes use of a Runge-Kutta method to solve the system over a specific time step. Specifically, the Dormand-Prince method (Dormand and Prince, 1980). In this work, the `ode45` function runs over 5 minutes intervals, with the solver applying a variable simulation step size within each interval.

4. Results

Figure 7 shows the average fit of the models to the data. Each row corresponds to one model (DTU, McGill, OHSU and Receptors¹), and each column shows the different visits (A, B and C). All models present a reasonable fit to the data, however the receptors model presents a better fit consistently across visits.

¹From this point on, we refer to the models by name but they comprise the combination of the baseline model plus the corresponding EGP model.

Figure 8 shows the average fit to plasma insulin and plasma glucagon data. Since both these signals belong to the baseline pharmacokinetics models, they are common for all the studied models. Plasma insulin graph for visit B presents some unusual shape in the standard deviation graph. This is because only one patient's data was measured at some of the depicted timestamps. Hence, the standard deviation is zero for those points.

The parameter values for the identification process are described in Tables 5 and 6. Table 5 shows the values for parameters that were identified per visit (S_T , S_D and the initial value of Q_2). Table 6 shows the parameters values of each EGP model for the eight patients.

RMSE results for each model and period are summarized in Figure 9. The RMSE values were analyzed at three different periods:

1. Considering the first part only (*First period*), from start time of the clinical trial until the glucagon bolus was administered ($t = -X$ to $t = 0$ min, see Figure 6). This interval was analyzed to ensure that the behavior of the baseline model was consistent independent of the EGP model.
2. From the moment the glucagon was administered, onward (*Second period*), from $t = 0$ to $t = 240$ min. This would be the main area of interest in this study, where the glucagon effect comes into play.
3. Along all the time of the experiment (*Overall*).

Table 4 details the mean RMSE (equation (8)) and its standard deviation for each of the models in each of the studied time periods. Several paired statistical analysis were performed, comparing each of the selected EGP models against the Receptors model. This comparison provided the result of the t -test, its p -value and Cohen's d size effect. Results in the First period show that there is no statistically significant differences between any of the studied models and the receptors model. However in the Second period, the difference is statistically significant for every pair of models. In the overall analysis, the pairs McGill-Receptors and OHSU-Receptors also present statistically significant differences. Across all the analysis it is also shown that the average error for the receptors model is lower in every comparison.

5. Discussion

This work's results show how the EGP model including glucagon receptors dynamics provides an improvement in describing the glucagon effect when compared with other models from literature. Table 4 reflects this result, showing a lower average error value for the Receptors model, and a statistically significant difference for each of the comparisons in the Second period, which is the main focus of our analysis. Also, Cohen's d values (larger than 0.8), confirm that there is a noticeable difference in the behavior between the analyzed pairs. In fact, for the Overall analysis, there is a statistically significant difference for all the comparisons

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Figure 7: Glucose simulation results. Figures show each of the studied models against the clinical data. Dashed/gray lines correspond to the data and continuous/colored lines show the simulation results. The central line for both data series represents the average of the eight patients, whereas the shaded area encloses standard deviation. Results show the response from $t = 0$ min to 240 min.

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Figure 8: Plasma insulin (top) and plasma glucagon (bottom) simulation results. Dashed/gray lines correspond to the data and continuous/colored lines show the simulation results. The central line for both data series represents the average of the the eight patients, whereas the shaded area encloses standard deviation. Results show the response from $t = 0$ min to 240 min. Irregularities in insulin standard deviation graph are due to just one patient's data being measured in certain timestamps, making zero the standard deviation.

Figure 9: Boxplots of RMSE values obtained per model for the First period of data (left), the Second period (middle) and Overall the time of the trial (right). White crosses mark mean values and black horizontal lines, median values.

but DTU-Receptors. However, the p -value is close to being lower than 0.05 and Cohen's d is also close to 0.8, meaning that the difference is not negligible.

Having no statistically significant difference in the First period agrees with what we expected, since in that interval,

the EGP model only contributes as a constant (basal value) to the general model. Our hypothesis was that no matter the EGP model used, the behavior in the First period should be similar across models in order to provide a fair comparison. The first period also shows the greater standard deviation in

the error values. This is due to the scarce data available in the first part of the experiment, which caused the fits to have greater RMSEs, and also the great variability in the initial conditions (i.e., there is no information about the patients' state prior to arriving to the clinic).

The results obtained in this study allow to incorporate EGP models including glucagon receptor dynamics into other type 1 diabetes simulators. To our knowledge, it has not been incorporated into any widely-used simulator but it could improve the accuracy of the *in silico* experiments, providing a more physiology-based definition.

One question remains unanswered and that is, how decisive the influence of plasma insulin levels is on the glucagon effect. As shown in Figure 8, plasma insulin levels were stable during the Second period, when glucagon was acting, with an average value of 15 mU/l approximately. According to the results reported by El Youssef et al. (2014), maintained high plasma insulin may impair glucagon effect. Their results report a high plasma insulin concentration around 40 mU/l, which is not close to the conditions of the clinical data used in this work.

Limitations of this work include: 1) the reduced number of participants ($n = 8$) in the clinical dataset. This is a general limitation found in metabolic studies addressing glucagon modelling where cohorts are typically between 10 and 20 (see for instance Ranjan et al. (2017); El Youssef et al. (2014); Castle et al. (2015)), due to the specific nature of the data to be collected in *ad-hoc* experiments (time series with frequent enough measurements of plasma glucose, insulin and glucagon are needed), as opposed to the use of tests part of the clinical routine such as the Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT), where larger cohorts are feasible (e.g. Contreras et al. (2020)). Hence, given the reduced number of datasets available, this only allows to draw preliminary conclusions. Further research will be needed introducing a larger dataset or several clinical trials as validation data in order to be able to guarantee the accuracy of the proposed model; 2) a slight inaccuracy in the first part of the data fit. As seen in Figure 7, some models did not exactly reach the point of interest at $t = 0$, which might also indicate a limitation in the insulin pharmacokinetics models; 3) The large number of parameters to be identified. A long time was needed to solve the optimization problem, which makes it infeasible to be solved online within an AP algorithm; 4) Further validation should include different datasets in a variety of conditions, such as larger glucagon doses, higher plasma insulin concentrations or close in time repeated glucagon doses.

6. Conclusions

This work presents a glucagon receptors based EGP model, and performs a head to head comparison with three other models from literature. The evaluation consists in identifying parameters from the selected EGP models to fit data from a clinical trial. The results show an improvement in the data fitting with the proposed model. These outcomes

will be useful in the study of T1D and AP development, allowing for more accurate *in silico* validations.

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Table 3

EGP models parameters and states description. Parameters marked with (★) are the ones to be identified.

Magnitude	Units	Description
k_{off}	min^{-1}	Dissociation rate
k_{rec}	min^{-1}	Recycling rate
k_{in}	min^{-1}	Internalization rate of the glucagon-bonded receptor
k_{on} ★	$(\text{pg}/\text{min})^{-1}$	Association rate of glucagon to the receptor
V_h	ml	Volume of the hepatic interstitial space
K_r ★	unitless	Apparent dissociation constant
V_r ★	$\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}/\text{min}$	Maximal glucagon-dependent hepatic glucose production rate
EGP_0 ★	$\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}/\text{min}$	EGP extrapolated to zero insulin concentration
S_I ★	$(\text{mU}/\text{l})^{-1}$	Hepatic insulin sensitivity
$r(t), r_C(t)$	unitless	Normalized amount of free and bonded receptors
$F_{hgp}(t)$	$\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}/\text{min}$	Hepatic glucose production
S_E ★	$(\text{mU}/\text{l})^{-1}$	Hepatic insulin sensitivity
E_{max} ★	$\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}/\text{min}$	Maximum EGP at basal insulin concentration
C_{E50} ★	pg/ml	Glucagon concentration yielding half of maximum EGP
G_{GNG} ★	$\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}/\text{min}$	Glucose production by gluconeogenesis
$G_{gg}(t)$	$\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}/\text{min}$	Glucose production due to glycogenolysis
S ★	$(\text{mU}/\text{l})^{-1}$	Insulin sensitivity
T ★	$(\text{pg}/\text{ml})^{-1}$	Glucagon sensitivity
G_{ng} ★	$\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}/\text{min}$	Effect due to gluconeogenesis
K_{Gd} ★	$(\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg})^{-1}$	Fractional deactivation rate constant
T_{Gd} ★	$\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}$	Glucagon rate of change sensitivity
$EGP_G(t)$	$\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}/\text{min}$	Contribution to EGP from the rate of change of glucagon
EGP_0 ★	$\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}/\text{min}$	Basal endogenous glucose production at zero insulin concentration
S_f ★	$(\text{mU}/\text{l})^{-1}$	Glucagon rate of change sensitivity
k_{g3} ★	min	
k_c ★	$(\text{ng}/\text{l})^{-1}/\text{min}$	Glucagon sensitivity
k_d ★	min^{-1}	Clearance rate of glucagon from the remote compartment
$Y(t)$	unitless	Effect of glucagon on EGP

Table 4

Means and standard deviations for the J_m index of each of the models against the receptors proposal, t -test analysis, and Cohen's d , separated by time period.

First period					
		Receptors	t	p	Cohen's d
DTU	7.22 ± 2.15	7.21 ± 2.36	0.02	0.985	0.01
McGill	8.84 ± 3.01		1.78	0.118	0.63
OHSU	8.64 ± 2.82		1.58	0.159	0.56
Second period					
		Receptors	t	p	Cohen's d
DTU	6.64 ± 1.58	5.90 ± 1.75	2.43	0.046**	0.86
McGill	7.18 ± 1.32		3.85	0.006**	1.36
OHSU	7.81 ± 1.75		3.06	0.018**	1.08
Overall					
		Receptors	t	p	Cohen's d
DTU	7.76 ± 1.45	7.13 ± 1.71	2.18	0.066	0.77
McGill	8.45 ± 1.38		3.44	0.011**	1.22
OHSU	8.99 ± 1.62		3.74	0.007**	1.32

Table 5

Identified values for the parameters S_I , S_D and Q_{20} . Bottom row shows the mean values and their standard deviation of each parameter.

Patient	Visit A			Visit B			Visit C		
	S_D	S_I	Q_{20}	S_D	S_I	Q_{20}	S_D	S_I	Q_{20}
1	$1.81 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-3}$	860	$5.45 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.82 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2061	$3.08 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.92 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2999
2	$1.52 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.89 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1038	$3.16 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.05 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1508	$2.78 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.59 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2178
3	$2.08 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2990	$5.32 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.83 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1939	$5.97 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.90 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2992
4	$1.16 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.60 \cdot 10^{-4}$	218	$2.74 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$7.43 \cdot 10^{-4}$	802	$3.55 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.12 \cdot 10^{-4}$	121
5	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.46 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1822	$9.64 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.19 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1126	$1.52 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.85 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1979
6	$2.79 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.50 \cdot 10^{-3}$	3000	$2.02 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	3000	$4.69 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.77 \cdot 10^{-3}$	3000
7	$1.46 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.65 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2190	$1.54 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.12 \cdot 10^{-3}$	3000	$1.23 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.28 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2042
8	$6.33 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.53 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2503	$2.60 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.32 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2177	$9.71 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.01 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2999
	$1.31 \cdot 10^{-4} \pm 9.60 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.37 \cdot 10^{-3} \pm 2.21 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1828 ± 1033	$2.80 \cdot 10^{-3} \pm 7.03 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.71 \cdot 10^{-3} \pm 1.44 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1952 ± 798	$4.47 \cdot 10^{-2} \pm 1.25 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$5.05 \cdot 10^{-3} \pm 2.87 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2289 ± 991

Table 6

Identified values for the DTU and McGill EGP models parameters. Bottom row shows the mean values and their standard deviation of each parameter.

Patient	DTU				McGill				
	S_e	E_{max}	C_{E50}	G_{GNG}	S	T	K_{Gd}	T_{Gd}	G_{ng}
1	$1.33 \cdot 10^{-2}$	100	900	5	0.01	0.05	0.26	$1.93 \cdot 10^{-1}$	7
2	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-3}$	75	999	6	0.01	0.05	0.01	$4.66 \cdot 10^{-3}$	6
3	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-3}$	100	447	8	0.03	0.20	6.88	$4.32 \cdot 10^{-1}$	9
4	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$	79	735	8	0.01	0.07	0.81	$3.65 \cdot 10^{-1}$	9
5	$2.98 \cdot 10^{-3}$	96	987	5	0.01	0.03	6.69	$5.54 \cdot 10^{-1}$	7
6	$1.00 \cdot 10^{-3}$	100	642	9	0.04	0.17	0.09	$4.16 \cdot 10^{-1}$	10
7	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-2}$	89	1000	3	0.01	0.05	6.65	$2.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$	3
8	$8.86 \cdot 10^{-3}$	100	631	1	0.01	0.06	0.07	$5.56 \cdot 10^{-1}$	5
	$6.34 \cdot 10^{-3} \pm 7.58 \cdot 10^{-3}$	92 ± 10	793 ± 209	6 ± 3	0.02 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.06	2.68 ± 3.37	$3.15 \cdot 10^{-1} \pm 2.24 \cdot 10^{-1}$	7 ± 2

Table 7

Identified values for the OHSU and Receptors EGP models parameters. Bottom row shows the mean values and their standard deviation of each parameter.

Patient	OHSU					Receptors				
	S_f	k_{g3}	k_c	k_d	EGP_0	S_r	k_{om}	K_r	V_r	EGP_0
1	$8.16 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.25 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.26	7	$1.33 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.25 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$	135	8
2	$9.19 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$9.81 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$7.46 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1.00	6	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.30 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.19 \cdot 10^{-1}$	200	9
3	$6.89 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$9.93 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.59 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.34	10	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.35 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.48 \cdot 10^{-2}$	195	10
4	$1.05 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.07 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.27	9	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.70 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.65 \cdot 10^{-2}$	80	10
5	$9.40 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$9.45 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.20	7	$2.98 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.04 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.86 \cdot 10^{-3}$	101	6
6	$9.98 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.23 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.69 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.32	12	$1.00 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.79 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$7.90 \cdot 10^{-3}$	109	10
7	$9.41 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.06 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.43 \cdot 10^{-2}$	1.00	3	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.72 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.04 \cdot 10^{-1}$	200	5
8	$1.35 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.33 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.46 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.13	5	$8.86 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.00 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$	103	4
	$3.92 \cdot 10^{-5} \pm 4.11 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.06 \cdot 10^{-5} \pm 1.62 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$4.11 \cdot 10^{-3} \pm 4.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.44 ± 0.35	7 ± 3	$6.34 \cdot 10^{-3} \pm 7.58 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.28 \cdot 10^{-3} \pm 1.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$4.94 \cdot 10^{-2} \pm 7.64 \cdot 10^{-2}$	140 ± 50	8 ± 2